

NUMERICAL MODELLING AND FULL-FIELD MEASUREMENT OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER BLAST LOAD

ir. M. A. Louar*^{1,2}, ir. B. Belkacem², ir. H. Ousji^{1,2}, Prof. Dr. ir. L. Pyl¹ and Prof. Dr. ir. J. Vantomme²

¹Department of Construction Engineering and Materials, Royal Military Academy, Belgium

²Department of Mechanics of Materials and Constructions, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Belgium

*Email: raouf.louar@rma.ac.be

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ABSTRACT

The dynamic response of Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRP) under blast loads is actively studied due to the increasing use of these materials and the arising risks of being subjected to accidental and intentional explosions. In the context of material identification by means of mixed numerical/experimental technics, the repeatability of the tests and the accurate modelling of the boundary and initial experimental conditions are key factors. The discussion of these two factors is the main topic of this paper. The results of a series of blast tests on fully clamped square glass fibre reinforced epoxy panels are presented. An explosive driven shock tube (EDST) is used to generate uniform blast loadings with different pressure-impulse combinations. First, experiments are performed on an assumed rigid target provided with pressure transducers to measure the pressure history and distribution which, also, allows assessing the planarity and repeatability of the loading. Then, the dynamic responses of the specimens are measured with a high-speed 3D-DIC system and the failure modes are described. The laminates are modelled in LS-Dyna using Belytschko-Tsay four-node shell elements and the loading is modelled with a pressure history distribution fitted from experimental measurements. The experimental measurements are compared to the numerical results for three material models with different failure criteria.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their numerous advantages and their versatility, composite materials are being more and more used in various fields. With this expand; the cases where composite materials are subjected to a blast wave from an accidental or intentional explosion are more frequent. Thus the study of the behaviour of composite materials under blast loading is a necessity. This subject is an area of active research. The blast response of several composites is studied such as E-glass fibres [1-5] with different resins: vinyl ester, epoxy or urethane, 3D woven S-2 glass fibres with epoxy/vinyl ester resins and Kevlar [1]. Another type of laminate composite materials tested for blast response is fiber metal laminates (FML) for instance, in [8, 9] GLARE panels are studied and in [10] glass-fiber polypropylene resin and aluminum laminates are tested.

The composite panels are tested to blast loading which is generally generated by a gas driven shock tube, but in some studies [8-10], it is generated by the detonation of HE at close range. The blast resistance of the materials is analyzed using different techniques: DIC [2, 4] to measure the real-time deformations, strain gauges [5, 6], ballistic pendulum [8], macroscopic and/or microscopic examination [1-8, 10] and residual compressive strength [3, 7].

The experimental study of real scale case is generally not possible for security or cost matter. So, finite element models are used to simulate the blast response of a structure. Generally, effective or homogenized material properties are used to model composite laminates instead of taking into account the individual component properties and geometrical arrangements. Many engineering problems are solved at macroscopic scale with such homogenized properties and the results are found satisfying. However, sometimes such analyses are not accurate enough and the microscopic approach is generally too complex to use. Hence, some multiscale methods for modeling composite materials have been developed [11]. They range from analytical methods, semi-analytical ones to purely numerical ones.

The choice of which method to use depends on the case studied, the means allocated and the precision required.

To model the layers in laminates, two types of elements are generally used: shell elements [1, 9] or solid elements [5, 10]. The use of shell elements is a simplification and is justified by the thickness of the layers in comparison to the in-plane dimensions [1]. But the authors in [12] presented a hybrid solid-shell element. These elements are eight noded with only displacement degrees of freedom and according to paper [12] assessment reveals that this element formulation provides very accurate results for a wide range of structural analyses making it suitable for the detailed local finite element analysis of laminated structures. Also, cohesive elements [10] or tie-break algorithms [9] are implemented to model the delamination damage mode and energy. The loading is generated using the ConWep module implemented in the different FE code used with a Lagrangian formulation or using a MMALE approach [9]. The MMALE approach gives a better structural stability than the ConWep approach but it requires more calculation time.

In the present paper, the dynamic response of E-glass reinforced epoxy laminates resulting from a blast load is investigated. The blast wave is generated by an explosive driven shock tube. First, the experimental setup is presented and the loading is experimentally examined with regard to the pressure-impulse combination and the spatial distribution. Then, the results from blast tests on E-glass reinforced epoxy laminates by means of two high-speed cameras in a stereoscopic configuration and 3D-DIC are discussed. Finally, a FE numerical model on LS-DYNA for the case study and a comparison between three material models and the experimental measurements are presented.

2 MATERIAL AND TEST SPECIMEN

One type of composite material is evaluated in the study for shock response: E-Glass / Epoxy composite. The matrix material is Resoltech 1070 epoxy. UD architecture is chosen for the E-Glass fibres. The plates are laminated using the hand layup technic with 6 layers at 0° and 90° ($[0^\circ, 90^\circ]_3$) and cured following the specification of the supplier. The areal weight of the $400 \times 400 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$ plates is 5.3 kg/m^2 .

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The EDST used in this study is a cylindrical steel tube with an inner diameter of 168.2 mm, a thickness of 4.5 mm and a length of 1200 mm. At the entrance, where the pressure is the most significant, the tube is reinforced over the first 200 mm with another steel tube of 193.7 mm inner diameter and 4.5 mm thickness (Figure 1). At the end of the tube, four pressure transducers are mounted to measure the pressure at two different sections of the tube and two different angular positions. The distance between two sensors is 80 mm and the distance between the last transducer and the end of the tube is 20 mm. The pressure sensors used in these tests are high frequency pressure transducers PCB QUARTZ ICP 102B04 with a sampling frequency of 5 MHz.

In order to evaluate the dynamic response of the plates under blast loading, two sets of tests are performed. In the first set, the loading is generated by the EDST; in the second, it is generated by a free air explosion. The square specimens, with a total surface of 400x400 mm² and a thickness of 4 mm, are clamped to the steel frame using bolts (see Figure 2) leaving a free area of 300x300 mm². On the face opposite to the loading, a high-contrast speckle pattern is applied on the specimens and the neighbouring area of the steel frame. Facing this side, two PhotronFastcam SA5 high-speed digital cameras (Figure 4.b) are placed in a stereovision configuration at a distance of 1.8 m from the frame. The aperture of both lenses (Nikon D80, 50 mm focal length f) is set to $f/5.6$ to keep the plate in focus during the test. The specimens are illuminated with 4 high intensity spotlights to balance the effect of the reduced aperture.

To avoid variations in the measurements due to temperature (heat from the spotlights) the lights are on until stabilization of the ambient temperature (between aeration and spotlights) but the specimens are covered before the beginning of the tests. The recording of the images at a frame rate of 25000 fps is triggered using a light intensity trigger oriented towards the explosive (Figure 1.a). The observed area is about 400x400 mm² and is imaged with 512x512 pixels, which gives a magnification factor of about 0.78 mm/pixel. An area of interest (AOI) of 200x200 mm² is considered for the correlation calculations. For correlation, a subset size of 21x21 pixels is used with a subset spacing of 3 pixels and a strain filter of 9. It has to be noted that several in-plane deformations are obtained from the DIC, and even if only one of the strains is shown at a time for brevity, the results are similar for the rest.

Figure 1: Experimental set-up: (a) high contrast speckle pattern and (b) EDST with frame

Figure 2: (a) Plate with speckle pattern, (b) dimensions and axes

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 Damage modes

First, tests are performed in order to evaluate the blast wave generated by the EDST. Charges ranging from 5 to 40 g of C4 are used. Figure 3.a chose a typical pressure signal obtained using a charge of 20 g of C4 at the entrance of the tube. The incident pressures and impulses with the relative variability in the measurements for the considered charges are illustrated in Figure 3.b and Figure 3.c.

Figure 3: (a) Typical reflected pressure signal, (b) incident pressures and (c) incident specific impulses with the variability in the measurement

Figure 4 shows the damage progression in the panels when subjected to blast loadings of increasing magnitudes. The panels exhibited damages ranging from moderate damage (15 g) to complete failure (40 g). Primary damage modes in the plates included fiber breakage (shear), tearing, boundary delamination and matrix cracking. Typical failure patterns are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Damage progression for increasing charges of C4: (a) 15 g, (b) 20g, (c) 30g and (d) 40g

Figure 5: Damage modes observed

4.2 DIC measurement

Due to the light from the detonation of the C4 charges, the sensors of the cameras are at some saturated as illustrated in Figure 6. This problem is more present with increasing charges. For this reason only the results from the test with 20 g of C4 are discussed in the rest of the paper. Figure 7 shows the displacement profile of the plates along the x-axis. It is clear the plate first undergoes a local indentation corresponding to the cross-sectional area of the EDST. Then, the profiles take a more conical shape. Finally, the conical shape becomes flatter until a final round profile is reached. The initial overall response is relatively symmetric. However; due to the damage propagation, the response becomes less symmetric.

The maximum values measured are about 45 mm for the displacement, 8% for the max. principal strain and 400 s^{-1} for the strain rate.

Figure 6: saturation of the optical sensor caused by the light from the fireball

Figure 7: Displacement profiles along the x-axis at different steps

3.2 Numerical model

The case study is modelled in the commercial software LS-DYNA using a Lagrangian approach and quadrilateral Belytschko-Tsay shell elements. The presumption of shell elements is fair enough regarding the thickness of the deformable plate. After a mesh study, the mesh size of the different parts is defined to $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ for the composite plate and to $20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$ for the rest. Fixed boundary conditions are applied at the four corners of the reinforcement bars. A tied nodes-to-surface contact algorithm with offset is implemented to model the interaction between the different parts. The nodes of the specimen in the blue area (slave nodes) are tied to the steel frame and the aluminium clamp which both act as master surface. For all parts, the middle surface is chosen as the reference surface. Therefore, the offset of the shell parts needs to be considered. Since only minor boundary delamination is observed in experiment, the composite plate is modelled with a single layer of elements and the number of plies and their orientation is implemented using the laminated theory. Three material models including different failure criterion are compared: MAT_54 with the Chang & Chang criterion, MAT_55 with the Tsai-Wu Criterion and MAT_58 with the Hashin criterion [14]. The material parameters (Table 1) used are obtained from quasi-static tests for tensile ones. Then, based the obtained values and the mixture law, the rests of the parameters are estimated.

Figure 8: (left) Front view and (right) back view of the FE model of the case study

Engineering constant		Value
E_1	[GPa]	28
E_2	[GPa]	12
ν_{12}	-	0.28
G_{12}	[GPa]	4
LT1	[GPa]	0.5
LC1	[GPa]	0.4
LT2	[GPa]	0.07
LC2	[GPa]	0.12
Sc	[GPa]	0.05

Table 1: Material parameters for the E-Glass/epoxy lamina

To apply the load on the specimen, a pressure profile with an exponential decay (Equation 1) with time is used to represent the pressure history. This pressure is assumed uniform over an area corresponding to the cross-sectional area of the tube while an exponential decay with distance from the center of the plate is used for the spatial distribution. This assumption is considered acceptable regarding the experimental measurement (Figure 9) of the reflected pressure performed using a rigid target with pressure transducers.

$$P(t) = P_0 (1-t/t_0) \exp(-t/a) \quad (1)$$

where P_0 is the reflected peak-pressure value and a is a positive wave form parameter.

$$P(x,y,t) = P(t) \exp(-k d) \quad (1)$$

where k is decay factor and d is the distance from the center of the plate.

Figure 9: Experimentally measured distribution of the pressure on the target plate with a charge of 20 g of C4 at $t=0.875$ ms

The measured and the calculated displacement curves for three points on the plate for the different material models are shown in figure 10. The three points have the coordinates (30,-30), (80,-80), and (120,-120) relatively to the axis in Figure 2.b. It is observed that the maximum values are close to each other but the time at which it is reached varies from one model to the other. The calculated permanent deflection is also close to the experimental one except for MAT_58 where the final deflection is small relatively to the others.

Figure 10: Comparison between the experimental and numerical displacement histories at three points

Figure 11 gives a comparison between the measured and calculated max. principal strain e_1 curves for three points, with the coordinates (30,-30), (80,-80), and (120,-120) relatively to the axis in Figure 2.b, on the plate for the different material models. Larger differences are observed than with the displacement curves. With MAT_55, the plate resistance is underestimated and several elements found to reach failure which reduces the stress propagation and strains. The maximum strains from MAT_58 are close to the experimental ones but the resistance of the plates is overestimated. Thus, the strains drop faster and to lower values than the experiment. Finally, MAT_54 results are close to the experiment in terms of maximum value but the permanent deformation is overestimated. These differences might be due the strain rate effect which is not taken in consideration in this preliminary study and to the defects in the plate material.

Figure 11: Comparison between the experimental and numerical e_1 strain histories at three points

Figure 12 show the max. damage fringes from FE analysis from MAT_54. The calculation with MAT_55 contain several eroded elements and with MAT_58 the resistance of the plate is over estimated and thus, are not presented here. It is observed that, with MAT_54, the transverse (matrix) damages in the diagonal direction and the borders are similar to the one observed in the experiments. However, It predicts failure in the longitudinal (fibre) direction which was not observed in the tests.

Figure 12: Damages from MAT_54 in (a) longitudinal tension, (b) transverse tension, (c) longitudinal compression and (d) transverse compression

9 CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, blast tests on E-glass reinforced epoxy laminates EDST and charges ranging from 15 g to 40 g of C4 are presented. The loading is experimentally assessed in terms of pressure, impulse, distribution and reproducibility. The dynamic response of the plates is measured using 2 high-speed cameras and 3D-DIC. The tests resulted in panel with moderate to complete failure. The measured blast response is investigated. The generated strain-rates reach 400 s^{-1} with a charge of 20 g of C4.

The case study is modelled in LS-DYNA using Belytschko-Tsay shell elements. The blast loading is applied as a pressure-time distribution which seems to be in good agreement with the pressure measurements. Three material models with different failure criterion are used and compared to the experimental measurements. The three material models are close to the experimental measurements from the displacement point of view. However, major differences are observed for the strains and the damage distribution. The Twai-Wu criterion in Mat55 underestimates the resistance of the laminate whereas the Hashin criterion in Mat 58 overestimates it. The Mat 54 (Chang & Chang criterion) gives the closest fit for this case.

REFERENCES

- [1] DANG X. and CHAN P.C., 2006, *Design and test of a blast shield for Boeing 737 overhead compartment*, Shock and Vibration 13, 629-650.
- [2] TEKALURE S.A., SHUKLA A. and RUGGERIO P., 2006, *Blast Loaded Thin Composite Plates - An Experimental Study*, SEM Annual Conference and Exposition on Experimental and Applied Mechanics.
- [3] HEBERT M., ROUSSEAU C. and SHUKLA A., 2008, *Shock loading and drop weight impact response of glass reinforced polymer composite*, Composite Structures 84, 199-208.

- [4] TEKALURE S.A., SHUKLA A. and SHIVAKUMAR K., 2008, *Blast resistance of polyurea based layered composite materials*, Composite Structures 84, 271-281.
- [5] LEBLANC J. and SHUKLA A., 2010, *Dynamic response and damage evolution in composite materials subjected to underwater explosive loading: An experimental and computational study*, Composite Structures.
- [6] PANKOW M., JUSTUSSON B., SALVI A., WAAS A.M., YEN C.F. and GHIORSE S., 2011, *Shock response of 3D woven composites: An experimental investigation*, Composite Structures 93, 1337–1346.
- [7] LEBLANC J., SHUKLA A., ROUSSEAU C. and BOGDANOVICH A., 2007, *Shock loading of three-dimensional woven composite materials*, Composite Structures 79, 344–35.
- [8] LANGDON G.S., CHI Y., NURICJ G.N., HAUPT P., 2009, *Response of GLARE panels to blast loading*, Engineering Structures 31, 3116-3120.
- [9] SOUTIS C., MOHAMED G. and HODZIC A., 2011, *Modelling the structural response of GLARE panels to blast load*, Composite Structures 94, 267-276.
- [10] THUC P.V., GUAN Z.W., CANTWELL W.J. and SCHLEYER G.K., 2013, *Modelling of the low-impulse blast behaviour of fibre-metal laminates based on different aluminium alloys*, Composites: Part B 44, 141-151.
- [11] KANOUTÉ P., BOSO D.P., CHABOCHE J.L. and SCHREFLER B.A., 2009, *Multiscale Methods for Composites: A Review*, Arch Comput Methods Eng 16: 31–75.
- [12] RAH K., VAN PAEPEGEM W and DEGRIECK J., 2013, *A novel versatile multilayer hybrid stress solid-shell element*, Comput Mech 51: 825–841
- [13] LADEVEZE P. and Le Dantec E., 1992, *Damage modelling of the elementary ply for laminated composites*, Composites Science and Technology 43: 257-267.
- [14] LS-DYNA Theory manual, March 2006.